

Research integrity
BEYOND bad apples
A European consortium
including three thematic networks

**BEYOND research ethics and integrity cases
for training young and/or early career
researchers (cases only)**

Project title: BEYOND BAD APPLES: Towards a Behavioral and Evidence-Based Approach to Promote Research Ethics and Research Integrity in Europe

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What is this about?

This document collects all the cases created by the BEYOND project to support training of young and/or early career researchers. In the index below trainers can find the complete list of all the cases (including tags).

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Dilemmas

Case N.1-Where does the salary come from?

Two grants for **researcher Silva** are about to end, and another grant is about to start, but at the request of the partner organisation, the start of the new grant has been postponed. For **Silva**, this means that there is not enough salary to pay a newly hired researcher for the next 4 months. At the same time, **researcher Jansen** has a grant with money left over, and in order not to pay it back, the money should be spent. **Jansen** comes to **Silva** to ask for advice – what to do with the leftover money?

What would you answer as researcher Silva?

1. I would recommend that Jansen read carefully the grant agreement – are there activities that have not been done or that could still be planned? The grant money should be used to fulfil the objectives of the grant.
2. I would suggest Jansen that they consider if there are colleagues who could be given additional work in connection with the grant and if they could use the grant money for this.
3. I would share with researcher Jansen my concern regarding the newly hired researcher and investigate whether it would be possible for Jansen to offer them work related to the grant for four months.
4. I would encourage researcher Jansen to return the resources to the funder if they cannot be used as intended.

Points to consider

- Financial issues – proper use of grant money, conditions of the funding (restrictions, repurposing options); the broader research funding practices in the institution. Are there instructions available from the institution that would guide the way towards a solution? Individual and institutional dangers of “creative accounting”, accountability in advising colleagues in matters of research funding.
- Respect for autonomy of the people involved in the case – Silva and Jansen, also the unnamed researcher (their opinion in the matter) and possible other people to whom the work could be offered to (their actual availability, their current workload, their other responsibilities to institution)
- Strategic planning and coordination – how to avoid similar issues in the future?

Keywords: finances, financial planning

Case N.2-Suspicious use of funds

Doctoral student **Erikson** works at **Professor Keller's** project. In addition to research duties, **Professor Keller** has tasked doctoral student **Erikson** with checking the grant's management documents. Doctoral student **Erikson** has been performing this task for some time when they notice that time sheets from people they don't know keep being added (time sheets are records of how many hours employee has spent on a particular project work, this is important for payroll and project management purposes). Although **Erikson** also works for the grant, they have not seen these persons or heard their names in any meeting. Now, filling in the tables, three new names were added again.

What would you do instead of Erikson?

1. Paying wages from grants to people who do not work in the grant is not allowed. I will report the matter to my supervisor's supervisor.
2. I believe that the supervisor has justified reasons for including those researchers in the project, therefore I wouldn't do anything.
3. I would turn to my supervisor Keller to find out what the added people are doing in the project. Then I'd know better how to make appropriate additions to the documents.
4. I would turn to the three added people and find out what they did in the project in more detail – I'd explain that I must accurately show the classification of their work in the documentation.

Points to consider

- Financial issues – proper use of grant money, conditions of the funding (restrictions, repurposing options); broader research funding practices in the unit and the institution. Individual and institutional dangers of “creative accounting”. Confidentiality often associated with financial issues.
- Responsibilities (financial and ethical ones) associated with one's position, potential conflicts of interest.
- Consideration of loyalties and power hierarchies affecting this situation.

Keywords: finances, financial planning, whistleblowing

Case N.3-Collaboration breakdown

Researchers **Becker** and **Moreno**, who work in different chairs, decided to cooperate and write a joint publication. Researcher **Becker** had collected biological material during the experiment, which researcher **Moreno** was ready to analyse outside of their direct duties. Researcher Becker wanted to get the results of the analysis quickly, but researcher Moreno could not finish the analyses quickly enough as they had a lot of other duties to fulfil. This led to quarrels, and relations between researchers deteriorated.

When researcher Moreno finally delivered results, researcher Becker wrote an article manuscript based on the results, which researcher Moreno supplemented with analysis results and drawings. However, while reviewing the manuscript, researcher Becker discovered that two drawings based on researcher Moreno's data were incorrect. Moreno apologized that it was a small mistake when pasting the drawing and made new drawings, but these also seemed suspicious to researcher Becker. Researcher Becker then requested that researcher Moreno share the data, and the algorithm used in the analysis. Researcher Moreno refused and stopped cooperating.

What would you do in place of researcher Becker?

1. I would turn to researcher Moreno again to get more clarity on the circumstances. I'd explain that if I do not get access to the raw data, I will file a complaint with the academic ethics committee regarding data fabrication against Moreno.
2. I would decide to do nothing more and focus on new projects. I don't have time to argue with researcher Moreno; if they do not want to get a publication, that's their decision.
3. I would turn to researcher Moreno again and try to find out what kind of help they would need so that getting from the raw data to the result could be correctly reflected in the article.
4. Researcher Moreno's behaviour seems questionable to me. I ask their supervisor to discuss whether I need to turn to the academic ethics committee and/or the university management to submit a complaint about unethical activities and data manipulation.

Points to consider

- Communication and cooperation: e.g., how to agree in a transparent and unambiguous way regarding responsibilities and expectations? Particularities of interdisciplinary cooperation.
- Current workload and enforceability of promises
- Conflict and disagreement resolution: what resources (mechanisms, established practices) are there on individual and institutional levels?
- Data: practices (disciplinary, departmental, institutional, policy-level) for handling of research data in a transparent and fair way
- Reporting possible misconduct: what options (i.e. existing guidelines) are there to raise concerns or to ask for advice/mediation?

Keywords: cooperation, data, trust

Case N.4-Who owns the algorithm?

The results of a joint study have been written into a manuscript, with all researchers as co-authors. When the manuscript is about to be submitted, **researcher Novak** informs the others that **researcher Costa** from his unit has asked for authorship too, because the data was analysed with the algorithm that he had created. Researcher Costa was not involved in this project. However, in a hurry, Novak had sought Costa's assistance because of Costa's extensive experience in data analysis and algorithm development. According to Novak, this was only technical assistance, such as drawing up graphs or translating text, and therefore she did not consider it necessary to inform the other authors of the article about researcher Costa's help. However, now a dispute has broken out, and researcher Novak is investigating whether other authors agree to include researcher Costa as an author.

To find a solution, she turns to the most experienced member of the working group, Professor Miller, whose opinion everyone respects.

How would you decide if you were Professor Miller?

1. In my opinion, such a demand is not justified. I'd turn to the head of researcher Costa's unit with the suggestion to discuss the principles of publishing ethics and authorship criteria with the unit's researchers.
2. I believe that without researcher Costa the publication would not have been completed, which is why his contribution was of value. I would also support naming him as an author because I see opportunities for future cooperation.
3. I believe that researcher Costa has contributed, and this deserves recognition regardless of what we think of the algorithm's affiliation. I'd be in favour of adding him as an author.
4. I think that not everyone who contributes to research fulfils authorship criteria but only those whose contribution was significant and who take full responsibility for the results. I would propose to thank researcher Costa in the acknowledgement section of the article.

Points to consider

- Communication and cooperation: e.g. how to agree in a transparent and unambiguous way regarding responsibilities and expectations? Particularities of interdisciplinary cooperation. Ensuring good communication practices in teamwork.
- Authorship: what are the relevant criteria (for particular discipline, for particular manuscript); how are authorships discussed, whose responsibility is it to raise this?
- Workloads and enforceability of promises, are the agreements and promises made in a timely manner or are things happening in a rush?
- Conflict and disagreement resolution: what resources (mechanisms, established practices, neutral third parties) are available on individual and institutional levels?

Keywords: authorship, cooperation, interdisciplinarity

Case N.5-An unreferenced method

Researchers Reed and Andersson published an article in which the method they developed for analysing biological material was described in detail. Sometime later, researcher Andersson was approached by another working group, who asked researcher Andersson to analyse their data using the same method and proposed to publish the results together. Researcher Andersson agreed and performed the analysis. The article was published, researcher Andersson was a co-author, but in terms of methodology, no reference was made to the article in which the method of analysis was described for the first time. Researcher Reed is concerned about this and requests that he be appointed as a co-author, because it is their commonly developed method.

What would you do in the shoes of researcher Andersson?

1. I would not agree. I'd explain to researcher Reed that the method is not protected by copyright and can be used freely.
2. I would not agree to add another author but I'd be willing to include a reference to our previous joint publication in the addendum of the already published article.
3. I would not want to spoil the good relationship with researcher Reed and I'd propose to discuss with all co-authors the possibility of recognizing researcher Reed's contribution.
4. It is difficult for me to impartially assess the conflict that has arisen. I would appeal to the Academic Ethics Committee to resolve the situation.

Points to consider

- Authorship: what are the relevant criteria (for particular discipline, for particular manuscript); how are authorships discussed, whose responsibility is it to raise this? Are there institutional or disciplinary guidelines available? What are alternative acknowledgement pathways to authorship?
- Management of research process: current workload and enforceability of promises (are the agreements and promises made in a timely matter or are things happening in a rush?) How to ensure sufficient attention and care to relationships within research processes? How to make decisions in transparent, inclusive and unambiguous way?
- Intellectual property and citation practices: how is intellectual property defined in this field and does it include methods? Are there rules and guidelines available that explain this?
- Conflict and disagreement resolution: what resources (mechanisms, established practices, neutral third parties) are available on individual and institutional levels?

Keywords: authorship, intellectual property, methodology, cooperation

Case N.6-Colleagues and co-authors

PhD student White has written a research paper with three other researchers in their native language, aspects of which could be of interest to the international scientific community. White is motivated to rewrite the paper in English and submit it to an important journal. White proposes this to co-authors, but they want no part in the project, having doubts about its feasibility and rationale.

White rewrites the paper and, submitting it, is faced with a question – how should the co-authors of the national version be recognised?

What would you do if you were White?

1. I would not make them co-authors – the two papers do differ and besides, my colleagues didn't agree to be associated with the project. I'd submit the paper as if it was fully authored by one person.
2. I would not mark them as authors because in a sense the issue is risky – the authors might be faced with a charge of self-plagiarism. I'd face the music alone and mention my colleagues in the acknowledgements.
3. Just to be sure, I'd ask the co-authors of the previous paper if they'd like to be named authors of the new article too. I'd act according to their wishes. Although they haven't contributed to the new publication, they have played a significant role in developing the previous article.
4. I'd definitely mark them down as authors because the new paper is based on their work too.

Points to consider

- Collegiality and cooperation – how to agree and disagree in transparent and unambiguous way that allows for future cooperation?
- Academic freedom – what are the research and publication practices in the discipline and/or institution? How much collaboration or coordination is expected? How explicit are these rules (for example, to younger researchers)?
- Authorship and publication ethics: publications in native and non-English languages, the issue of self-plagiarism. How are authorship agreements achieved, how are they negotiated and documented, are there processes or guidelines in place to help resolve disputes? Issues of gift authorship and denied authorship.
- Conflict and disagreement resolution: what resources (mechanisms, established practices, neutral third parties) are available on individual and institutional levels?

Keywords: authorship, translation

Case N.7-Reporting questionable behaviour?

Storm has previously worked as an expert in the field of law enforcement but has now started working as a lecturer and researcher. Storm and colleagues have formed a research group to study the daily activities of prisoners. An important part of the study is participant observation that is conducted in prison.

Storm has already visited the prison several times. One day he witnesses how one officer is clearly upset with a prisoner. As the observation day continues, Storm notices the same officer yelling at the prisoner.

What would you do if you were Storm?

1. I would intervene in the situation and find out if I can ask the prisoner for details about their daily activities.
2. I would not report the official, because I am concerned that if I share my observations, I will not be allowed to continue the participatory observation and the study will fail. Supervision and training of officials is a responsibility of the agency.
3. I would not report the officer because I do not want the prison officer to be punished because of me.
4. Although as an observer I have no obligation to report what I saw to the agency, I would try to arrange a meeting with the officer's superior to share my observation.

Points to consider

- Responsibilities of researcher to various stakeholders – research participants, partner institutions, other researchers. This includes both ethical and legal duties, for example confidentiality or duty to report (misconduct). Special responsibilities might be due to vulnerable participants. Are there institutional guidelines or counsellors who could be approached for advice?
- Research integrity – duties to oneself as a good professional researcher, what does that entail? Reflexivity on one's own background (in this case law enforcement) and motivation.
- Management of research process: preparation for potential risks, dealing with incidental and unexpected findings or aspects of research, research ethics protocols. Are there institutional and disciplinary guidelines? Have these issues been pre-emptively addressed, for example in the research application?

Keywords: qualitative methods, whistleblowing

Case N.8-Plagiarism among the Faculty

Smith is a young researcher who has just been appointed to the university committee that handles misconduct cases. During the monthly meeting a decision must be made on how to proceed with allegations about a prominent and internationally respected **researcher Lund** who has supported the university throughout their long, prolific career.

A reviewer of research proposals had noticed that Lund had used materials from other authors without citing them. The application was rejected, and a notification was sent to the university committee with the full review including the list of related works which should have been cited.

During Lund's long career, there have been rumours as well as a few overt accusations concerning plagiarism. However, all of these have been refuted as false accusations.

Lund is currently in charge of planning further large research projects that are very important to the university and is associated with several ongoing ones. As a senior researcher at the university, they have supervised many of the universities' employees.

If you were Smith, a member of the committee, what would you recommend the committee to do?

1. I find that the received materials are solid proof of academic fraud. I would support making the case public in the university and communicating openly that we don't tolerate plagiarism. I'd support warning the researcher that if they violate the rules again, they will be fired.
2. Since the application has already been rejected and other research misconduct cases have not been investigated but stayed on the level of rumours without official complaint being made, I would support not proceeding with the case as the researcher has already suffered consequences (not getting the funding).
3. I'd support solving the case privately, i.e. the committee head would have a private conversation with the researcher, listen to their viewpoint and condemn them for their carelessness.
4. I'd support the decision to form a committee to gather more information on the researcher's previous projects and publications. If more evidence pointed to plagiarism, I would support bringing proceedings against the researcher regarding academic fraud.

Points to consider

- Handling allegations of research misconduct; existence of guidelines and procedures; transparency and accountability of the process, including timelines, conflict management.
- Loyalty issues in the organisation, in smaller and larger teams.
- Whistleblowing procedures in the organisations (regarding previous allegations).

Keywords: whistleblowing, research misconduct, research misconduct investigation, plagiarism

Case N.9-The interviewee sets limits

Karol is the representative of his organisation in an international research project funded by the European Commission, the purpose of which is to study future surveillance technologies. As part of other activities, interviews will be conducted among police officers from the represented countries. It has been explained to the interviewees that the purpose of the study is theoretical and mapping development trends, the participants remain confidential, and the results are presented in a generalised form.

The planned interviews have been conducted, and the analysis of the results will begin soon. One day, Karol is contacted by a police officer who gave the interview a few weeks earlier. They ask not to use excerpts from their interview in reports. They explain that although they still agree with the use of interview for analysis, they have concluded, as a result of discussions with their colleagues, that the information they provided should be treated as confidential and quotes should not be presented in reports, articles or elsewhere. When asked if they want to withdraw the interview, they explain that they do not, because they still consider it important to share the relevant information.

What do you do instead of Karol?

1. I would do as the interviewee wishes and write a note on the interview transcription in the database regarding it being confidential information.
2. I would promise the interviewee that their quotes will not be used, and I write to the coordinator about the corresponding restriction.
3. I would remove the interview from the database because I don't see how it would be possible to guarantee during the analysis that I or other colleagues are not quoting them.
4. I would try to convince the interviewee to let us use the quotes, because the data is analysed and the quotes are presented confidentially.

Points to consider

- Institutional and national legal policies and traditions on public funding and public interest.
- Confidentiality and protection of the interests of research participants; how to balance that with transparency requirements and researchers' duties to other stakeholders?
- Relationship with the client – communication, loyalties and procedures for resolving disagreements.
- Integrity of the research and the researcher.

Keywords: confidentiality, qualitative methods

Case N.10-Secrecy of results

Lemmit oversees a study within Europe, which has been commissioned by a public sector institution. The stages of the research agreed upon in the procurement have been implemented, all steps have been discussed with the client, and the draft of the research report is being discussed with the client. During the meeting, the client explains that since the results presented in the report are sensitive, the report must be treated as confidential, and the final report must be marked as such.

What would you do in Lemmit's place?

1. I would agree with adding confidentiality-clause because the results are sensitive.
2. I would ask the client to clarify what information they consider sensitive and delete these sections of the report so that it is possible to publish a public version of the report (in addition to the main report containing sensitive data).
3. I believe that the report should be publicly available as it is publicly funded, and I would write the more sensitive results in a general enough way that the report can be documented without the confidentiality clause.
4. I would prepare a detailed report. I would consult with the head of my institution about what to do about confidentiality-clause as I consider it important to publish the report in its entirety.

Points to consider

- Institutional and national legal policies and traditions on public funding and public interest.
- Confidentiality and protection of stakeholder interests; how to balance that with transparency requirements and researchers' duties to other stakeholders?
- Relationship with the client – communication, loyalties and procedures for resolving disagreements.
- Integrity of the research and the researcher.

Keywords: confidentiality, research participants, public interest

Case N.11-Researcher as an activist

Martens is a young researcher who has been invited to serve as a reviewer in the NGO-s funding committee. One of the proposals Martens has approved has now come to public attention – in the proposal an academic environmental researcher proposed to write a book about climate change for the public but when the book was published, it was suspicious about the claims of human agency in climate change and critical of the many policy initiatives that have been put into place to counteract the effects of climate change.

The NGO is dissatisfied with the quality and tone of the book, and they are collecting the opinions of the reviewers who supported the book on whether it fulfils the promises made in the proposal and whether the NGO should ask the money back. Martens has read the book and finds the proposal to be somewhat misleading but not outright false.

What would you suggest if you were Martens?

1. Since in my opinion the book is not fundamentally different from the proposal, I would support not asking the money back. Not all projects are successful.
2. Although the book is not fundamentally different from the proposal, I would find it to be misleading and support asking the money back.
3. The researcher is likely not able to return the money, therefore there is no point in asking the money back. The damage is already done and the more attention the book gets, the more it will be read.
4. I'd support asking the money back as it would provide the funds to publish another, more science-based publication.

Points to consider

- Integrity, honesty and transparency of the stakeholders involved (as individuals and organisations).
- Academic freedom and accountability – how should these be balanced?
- Professional obligations and identity.

Keywords: research integrity, research funding, accountability

Case N.12-Citizen science and activism

PhD student Stanton's research focuses on the butterfly populations in a particular mountain valley. The research project involves also a group of active locals as citizen scientists – they are trained to recognise different butterflies and invited to log their sightings into the database. Cooperation goes very well with a trustful relationship being established between the researcher and the environmentally conscious locals.

One day a local businessman comes out with a plan to build new residences in the valley. In the community, concerns grow because of the environmental impact of this development. The same group of citizen scientists turn to Stanton and ask the researcher to publicly oppose the project with an argument based on the worsening conditions for local fauna. While Stanton does believe that the building of new residences worsens the environment for the butterflies somewhat, they do not think that this is very significant.

What would you do if you were Stanton?

1. I would discuss with the community about the upsides and downsides of building the residences. I would explain that the impacts are not very significant in my opinion.
2. Although I understand the community, I would decide to distance myself from the situation as I am a scientist not an activist.
3. I would agree with the community and put out a detailed and explicit statement on why the new residences should not be built.
4. I would suggest having a meeting between the community and the developer of the residences that I would offer to facilitate – this way both sides can come together to find a compromise in this situation.

Points to consider

- Relationships with the citizen scientists' group but also with other stakeholders in the community as well as with one's professional colleagues.
- Research integrity and identity of a researcher.
- Ethical issues of citizen science – neutrality vs advocacy issues, the opportunities and perils of public engagement.
- Conflicts of interest and how can these be avoided?

Keywords: citizen science, research integrity, conflict of interest, activism, advocacy

Case N.13-Funding decision

Marke is an expert reviewer in a funding body. In a new round of grant decisions, the reviewers are instructed to create their own ranking list of the projects. Marke has read through all the assigned projects, provided feedback and points and is now reviewing the first version of the ranking list. Marke notices that the first and the second project in the list got the same number of points and now Marke needs to decide how to rank them. When re-reading the projects, it emerges that one of the projects states their use of AI in project writing and lists all the elements AI was used for (brainstorming, structuring, editing), while the second project does not mention any use of AI. The funding body has not indicated any rules about the use of AI, but they have stated that transparency as regards using AI is a must.

How would you list the projects if you were Marke?

1. Since there are no rules listed for using AI besides transparency, I would try to find another point from the assessment guide to differentiate between the projects.
2. I believe that most researchers use AI in one or another way and therefore I would give extra credit to the project that is transparent about its usage.
3. Since I don't know if the second project used the AI or not, I would ask the funder if they have any information on that matter and ask for advice how to proceed with the information.
4. I trust that both projects were transparent in the proposals, and therefore I think the project that did not use AI should be rewarded for that (i.e. not using shortcuts).

Points to consider

- Ethical concerns around evaluation: transparency and consistency of evaluation and decision-making process, proper documentation and good quality guidelines, fairness and objectivity in assessment, decision-making in the context of incomplete information.
- Concerns around AI: the fast pace of development of AI, lack of concrete guidelines or policies, biases concerning (the use of) AI.

Keywords: AI, funding, fairness, objectivity, grant evaluation

Case N.14-Two PhD students

Doctoral student Rossi has gathered tons of video material on their research topic on very elderly people (average age of participants 102). Before gathering data, the student asked all interviewees for written consent confirming that the material would only be used in the dissertation and not shown to third parties. Its contents would remain confidential. The consent form did not address the issue of further research.

The PhD student gathered data for two years. After some time, **another PhD student, Summers**, who is researching the same field, turns to Rossi, asking to use their transcriptions of the video material. Summers finds that the material contains valuable data, and gathering this information again would be a pointless waste of resources, not to mention impossible with the same group as they have all passed away. Rossi refuses to share the material, referring to the agreement with the subjects of the research. Rossi is willing to make an exception if Summers names them co-author in all publications that use Rossi's data. Summers refuses that offer and goes to their supervisor Brown, who also supervises PhD student Rossi.

What would you do if you were supervisor Brown?

1. I'd support PhD student Rossi and assure them that they have every right to turn down Summers' proposal.
2. I'd support student Summers as it would be impossible to collect this data again since research participants have died. If the co-authorship is the price for this, I suggest them to come to an agreement.
3. I'd tell PhD student Rossi that consent can be interpreted in many ways – they could agree with the other student's proposal.
4. I'd support both students to find a way for working together. The data cannot be collected again but there is another perspective that can be derived from there, a joint approach can be agreed upon both in using the data and in assigning authorship.

Points to consider

- Informed consent, its foundations, purpose and implications.
- Data sharing and access – the legal and ethical regulations affecting research, opportunities for Open Science and collaboration

Keywords: informed consent, cooperation, data sharing

Case N.15-A tutor in a bind

Doctoral student Tamm has reached the final stages of writing their thesis, with one last publication ready to be submitted to a journal. Tamm is in a hurry to graduate, as the research project funding their studies is nearing its end.

Tamm is supervised by **researcher Berger**, who is also a co-author of the manuscript. However, Berger feels that their communication with Tamm is increasingly strained, as Tamm does not heed Berger's advice. Consequently, Berger, as both supervisor and co-author, is dissatisfied with the quality of Tamm's work and believes the article is not suitable for publication in its current form. Not publishing the article would delay Tamm's defence significantly, likely resulting in a period of unemployment after the project's conclusion.

What would you do instead of researcher Berger?

1. I feel that I cannot be the author of an article that is not ready for publication. I would ask to be removed as an author.
2. I believe that the reviewers' criticism is a good lesson for PhD student Tamm. I would let them send a half-baked article for peer review.
3. I propose rewriting the article myself in a suitable way, adding myself as the first author and PhD student Tamm as the second author, and then sending the article for review.
4. I would not do anything, because I don't want to spoil my relationship with PhD student Tamm. I would promise to send the article for review when the doctoral student is convinced of its readiness.

Points to consider

- Good practices of supervision and mentoring and of quality of research, responsibilities of the supervisor and of the supervisee.
- Conflict and disagreement resolution, possibility of finding a neutral advisor.
- Life after PhD.

Keywords: supervision, research quality, conflict resolution

Case N.16-Be honest with the instructor?

The supervisor of **students Martin and Larsen's** bachelor thesis was **researcher Ellis**, who involved the students in the implementation of an applied science project. The students were very satisfied and each of them completed and successfully defended their bachelor's thesis within the project. They hoped to continue with the subject they were interested in under the same supervisor in the master's program.

Before the start of admission to the master's program, a research conference was held in the field, where researcher Ellis presented the applied science project. In the presentation the results of the students' bachelor's theses were given but they were never mentioned (nor that part of the work was done by the students as part of their bachelor's work). Students Martin and Larsen were proud that their work was also presented to the audience, but at the same time, they felt that their contribution should have been mentioned as well. Student Larsen said that he did not want to talk to the supervisor about an uncomfortable topic and would prefer if student Martin did nothing either.

What would you do in place of student Martin?

1. I find it unfair that our contribution is not mentioned. I would turn to supervisor Ellis and say honestly what I think about the case.
2. Do nothing. I want to continue with the same topic in my master's degree and raising this potentially uncomfortable topic would jeopardise my future.
3. Do nothing because fellow student Larsen is not willing to raise an uncomfortable topic.
4. I suspect that such disagreements with the supervisor may still arise in the future, and it is more reasonable to end the cooperation with researcher Ellis. I would look for a new potential instructor and topic.

Points to consider

- Collaboration and the power dynamics in supervisor-student relationships.
- Authorship and what counts as proper credit or acknowledgement in various academic formats.

Keywords: cooperation, authorship, mentoring

Case N.17-Reintegration of the researcher

Ollie, an established researcher with an excellent academic track record, was unexpectedly arrested and later found guilty of espionage. After serving their sentence, Ollie is now seeking employment and has approached various colleagues and former research partners. Among those contacted is Sam, a senior colleague from another institution with whom Ollie had previously collaborated successfully.

Ollie's arrest and conviction came as a shock to their colleagues. Despite the past incident, Ollie is determined to reintegrate into the scientific community and to continue their research career, believing that with the sentencing the punishment has been completed. Ollie reaches out to **Sam**, hoping to leverage their previous positive working relationship to secure a new position.

What would you do if you were Sam?

1. I would support hiring Ollie as they have served the punishment and there is no need for additional punishment.
2. I would not support hiring Ollie as this would undermine the public trust in our activities.
3. I would support offering Ollie activities they can perform but would not hire them as permanent member of the staff.
4. I would not support hiring Ollie, but since we have had previous good collaboration together, I would offer a very good letter of recommendation on my behalf.

Points to consider

- Rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers: on what conditions?
- Trust in collaboration: how can trust be rebuilt?
- Academic reputation of individuals and institutions, what affects it? Who has responsibility to protect it?

Keywords: rehabilitation, reintegration, collaboration, trust

Case N.18-A research ethics scandal

Dr Fyn is a leading researcher in their field. In addition to university research, Fyn also fulfils various advisory roles outside university. During winter exam session one investigative journalism programme airs a story accusing one of the non-governmental organisations, where Fyn is serving as member of council, of gross research misconduct. The public is outraged, and the university also reprimands Fyn. Fyn apologises for the misconduct of the NGO but claims publicly that they personally are not responsible.

Dr Helge is a young researcher who just defended their PhD in the same field as Dr Fyn. Since they have met during Dr Helge's studies, Dr Fyn contacts Dr Helge and proposes a joint research project.

What would you do if you were Dr Helge?

1. I would not agree to the joint research as my research might be compromised by the reputation of Dr Fyn.
2. I would agree to work with Dr Fyn, if I would be the lead researcher of the project and Dr Fyn would be in an advising position.
3. I would agree to work with Dr Fyn, because they have already been reprimanded for their inactions by the public, and I find it to be enough.
4. I would not agree to work with Dr Fyn yet as they have not taken full responsibility for their inactions by suggesting someone else is responsible. However, I do not rule out the possibility of working with them after some time has passed – to see, if they have learned their lesson from this scandal.

Points to consider

- Collaboration practices and power dynamics within academic sphere.
- Multiple roles of academics, their potential overlaps as well as conflicts of interest, duty of oversight.
- Reintegration issue – what are fair and sufficient sanctions, what are the responsibilities of involved stakeholders including other researchers, options for restoring research integrity?

Keywords: misconduct, conflict of interest, reintegration

Case N.19-Colleague's accusation

Research fellow Bright approaches the head of their research group, **Professor Smith**, to complain about the behaviour of their colleague, **research fellow North**. Bright reports that students have observed North behaving indecently and staggering around during university's Spring Days celebrations. Bright asserts that this is not the first such incident and believes that North's behaviour violates the principles of good scientific practice, undermines the integrity and reliability of the research institution, and sets a poor example for students. Bright insists that immediate action is necessary, stating that it is difficult to work with North under these circumstances and threatens to file an official complaint if no action is taken.

Professor Smith then speaks with research fellow North, who acknowledges that the events might have occurred as described by Bright but argues that such behaviour does not constitute a violation of research integrity. North contends that accusing them of damaging academia is unfair and malicious. They emphasise that their personal time is their own and that recent work-related stress has contributed to their actions.

What would you do if you were Professor Smith?

1. I'd feel the conflict needs to be solved but I could not objectively assess the situation myself. I'd delegate the case to the head of department.
2. I'd try to mend things between the co-workers, stressing that our joint goal is to complete the research project. After that we could discuss if long-time cooperation is in the cards.
3. I'd explain to Bright that what research fellow North does in their free time is private business and has nothing to do with research integrity. I'd ask them not to submit an official complaint as that would only harm our work relationship.
4. I'd agree with research fellow Bright's critique and warn North against such behaviour – serious consequences might follow and their career at the institution might suffer.

Points to consider

- Integrity and professional conduct, private and professional lives and academic reputation (of researchers and institutions)
- Responsibilities of researchers, mentors and colleagues
- Conflict resolution and available options for supporting researchers

Keywords: integrity, professional conduct, conflict resolution

Case N.20-Social media research and AI

Alex's post-doctoral project involves researching the mental health issues of university students through public social media postings. Alex has chosen three largest universities in the country for research and has acquired the research ethics committee approval for data collection.

Alex has collected massive amount of data and is struggling to analyse it. During one training Alex learns about a possibility of using free AI-software to analyse the data collected from social media. Alex is now contemplating this option.

What would you do if you were Alex?

1. I would not use the AI-software as it is not clear to me how the AI-software would manage (analyse, manipulate, record etc.) the data.
2. I would use the AI-software as I trust it to be sufficiently tested, my research would then result in important new knowledge and bring practical applications for the target group.
3. I would seek help from a co-worker in order to decide whether to use AI-software or whether to hire someone to help analyse the data in other ways.
4. I would reach out to the university to see if there are options to use other, perhaps more secure AI-software that the university could buy access to.

Points to consider

- Privacy and consent issues in social media and sensitive data usage, involvement of potentially vulnerable subjects.
- Use of AI in research – training opportunities for use of AI in research, transparency and accountability in AI use, the validity of research results.
- Research ethics approval and potential changes in research.

Keywords: AI, social media, ethics committee

Case N.21-Responsibilities for research misconduct

As an **early-career researcher**, **Opal** has been elected to serve on the university council. Among its responsibilities, the council provides recommendations on cases handled by the university's research integrity office. Current case discussed involves **Pat Green**, a prominent researcher leading a world-class biotech lab at your university. They faced allegations of data manipulation in several published papers where they were a co-author.

An independent investigation was conducted by the research integrity office to examine the integrity of Prof Green's research. The investigation revealed that while they did not personally engage in fraud or falsification of scientific data, there were significant flaws in the research conducted by their lab. Specifically, some members of the lab had engaged in inappropriate manipulation of research data. Prof. Green acknowledged that the many responsibilities they held as a professor, head of the lab, and co-owner of a successful biotech company, meant that they were not always able to cross-check research. Prof Green stated in the case report that they accepted the resulting shortcomings as their own and decided to leave the decision about their future with the university council.

If you were Opal, what would be your stance at the university council?

1. I would find that although Prof Green was not personally guilty of research misconduct, they were still responsible for it as the head of the lab, and they should be sanctioned.
2. Since Prof Green is not personally implicated in research misconduct, it is important to identify who is directly responsible and ensure that appropriate actions are taken against those individuals, following a thorough investigation.
3. I believe that Prof Green accepting responsibility is a sufficient consequence in this case. Therefore, I would support refraining from pursuing any further actions against them.
4. I would find the situation in the lab to be worrisome and recommend conducting a broader investigation at a systemic level to assess whether there are underlying issues affecting the upholding of research integrity across university laboratories.

Points to consider

- Accountability in research success and failure – for individual researchers, supervisors and institutions.
- The pressures of contemporary academic life, the possibility of slow science and options for the restoration of research integrity.

Keywords: misconduct, misconduct investigation, academic leadership